

Irrigation and water management

IR20 performance under different irrigation regimes

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We evaluated the effect of different irrigation regimes on grain and straw yield in an experiment at ARS, Bhavanisagar, in 1983 kharif. Three irrigation regimes were tested: the standard water supply rate provided by the Public Works Department to rice in the command area — 3.1 cm deep on alternate days; the recommended rate of the Water Management Scheme — 2.5 cm deep on alternate days; and 50% of the Public Works Department supply rate — 1.55 cm deep on alternate

Effect of irrigation regime on yield and water use efficiency of IR20, Bhavanisagar, India.

Treatment	Water use for nursery (mm)	Water use for field preparation (mm)	Treatment irrigation (mm)	Total water applied ^a (mm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency (kg/mm per ha)
3.1 cm on alternate days	62.5	200	1060	1322.5	5.2	4.7	3.93
2.5 cm on alternate days	62.5	200	838	1100.5	5.2	4.6	4.73
1.55 cm on alternate days	62.5	200	487	749.5	5.5	4.9	7.34
CD at 5%					ns		

^aExcludes effective rainfall, which was less than 10% of irrigation water applied.

days. The experiment was in eight replications in a randomized block design.

Grain and straw yields of IR20 were essentially equal for all treatments. The 1.55-cm rate produced highest grain and straw yield — 5.5, and 4.9 t/ha. Under

that irrigation regime, total water consumption, excluding effective rainfall, was 749.5 mm and water use efficiency was much higher (7.34 kg/mm per ha) (see table). □

Soil and crop management

Application methods to improve phosphorus uptake in rice

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Rice crop recovery of added P seldom exceeds 20%. We sought to determine methods of P application that would improve plant uptake of P in a wet season experiment at Madurai.

IR20 was planted in a red sandy clay loam soil (Typic Haplustalf). Treatments are in the table. The recommended dose of 120-26-50 kg NPK/ha was applied. N was applied as urea in two splits and K was applied basally as muriate of potash. The phosphate slurry was prepared by mixing 13 kg P/ha as single superphosphate 1:1 in a puddled soil. Seedling roots were dipped before transplanting,

Grain yield and response, uptake, and recovery of P as influenced by different application methods, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Response (kg /grain/ kg P)	Total uptake (kg/ha)	Recovery (%)
Control	4.1	—	23	—
Full dose as basal	4.6	20	28	8
Basal + foliar	5.0	34	34	12
Foliar	4.7	44	28	18
Slurry	5.2	85	28	19
Slurry + basal	4.8	18	32	11
Slurry + basal + foliar	5.3	30	36	15
Slurry + foliar	5.0	33	31	15
(CD P = 0.05)	0.1		3	1

and a foliar application of diammonium phosphate was applied.

Grain yield, and P uptake, response, and recovery are in the table. Grain yield was from 4.1 to 5.3 t/ha. Highest yield was with slurry dipping with P applied basally and in a foliar spray. That application method was estimated to save 67% of P fertilizer applied. High grain response

to slurry dipping may have been because it placed P in the effective root zone and encouraged uptake.

P uptake ranged from 23 to 36 kg/ha. Highest uptake was with slurry dipping with P applied basally and as a foliar spray. P recovery varied from 8 to 18%. Basal application gave lowest recovery and slurry dipping gave highest recovery. □